

Dhiruben Patel's *Rainbow at Noon (Agantuk)*: Sannyasi's Life Journey to Self-Realization

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Abstract: This paper is focused on a journey of Sannayasi's life and how he get self-realization and the modern society how treats sanyasi.

Keywords: Ashrma, Dhiruben, Gujarati, Rainbow, *sannyasi*

Dhiruben Patel's *Rainbow at Noon* was originally written in Gujarati entitled, *Agantuk*, it won the Sahitya Akademi Award, and Raj Supe translated English edition. Dhiruben Gordhanbhai Patel was born on 29th May 1926, her father Gordhanbhai Patel was a journalist for the 'Bombay Chronicle'. Gangaben Patel was a political activist and member of the All-India Congress Committee. Her family belongs to Dharmaj village near Anand. She grew up and still resides in Santacruz, a suburb of Mumbai. She was educated at the Poddar School in Mumbai and completed higher education at Elphinstone College. She completed a B.A. in English in 1945 and M.A. in 1949 from Bhavan's College. She taught English in college at Dahisar in 1963-64 and later taught English literature at the Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan. She temporarily worked with Anand Publishers. Subsequently, she founded Kalki Prakashan, a publishing house in 1963-64. She edited *Sudha*, a Gujarati journal from 1966 to 1975. She later served as the President of the Gujarat Sahitya Sabha. She served as the President of the Gujarati Sahitya Parishad in 2003-2004 and one of her plays, *Bhavani Bhavi* has been adapted into a film. Dhiruben Patel has written several collections of short stories and poetry as well as novels. She has written radio plays and staged plays. Her works were influenced by Gandian philosophy, she does not consider herself a feminist like the novelist Kaundanika Kapadia and she believes that the root cause of women's inferior status lies in their mental condition. Her early works deal with the lives of women and their relationships. Her later works have been primarily for children and young adults. Dhiruben Patel initially wrote in Gujarati, her novel *Agantuk* was translated

by Raj Supe into English as *Rainbow at Noon* in 2011. Her recent collection of poetry *Kitchen Poems* is in English, it was first recited by her at the Neemrana Literary Festival in 2002. These were later published and translated into German by Peter D O'Neil, and into Marathi, by Usha Mehta. She received Ranjiram Suvarna Chandrak in 1980, K. M. Munshi Suvarna Chandrak in 1981, and Sahitya Gaurav Puraskar in 2002, both by Gujarat Sahitya Akademi. She received the Nandshankar Suvarna Chandrak and Darshak Award in 1996. She won the Sahitya Akademi for Gujarati language in 2001 for her novel *Agantuk*.

Rainbow at Noon describes the life of Ishaan, a *sannyasi* or monk, who returns to his family after years away due to circumstances that arise at his ashram after the passing away of his Guru. It is a brilliant account of the inner turmoil of every man who wishes to rise above himself. It is mostly Ishaan's internal dialogue with himself, as he navigates the choppy waters of his return, made so by the initial disdain and incredulity of his very worldly family and later on by their intrusive greed & hunger for fame by association. He ponders the meaning of life and love, the nature of attachment, and the trappings of society. Interestingly, solace and succor come from the children in the book as they often do in real life. They seem instinctively to understand his need for solitude, his inability to make small talk, his desire to stay aloof, or rather, restrict his interaction with humanity to the minimum, so as to avoid attachments and resultant complications. They allowed him to be himself, afforded him space, and accepted him.

Rainbow at Noon began with the description of life journey as well as train journey. Ishan is a *Sannyasi*, he traveled to Bombay. He is the central character of the novel, he was allowed the mind and he was struggling to retain the past. His co-passengers woke up and sat on the lower berth, he occupied the window seat. He would see the faint morning light, the other two were absorbed in their conversation. The Boravi station appeared an half of a compartment emptied. Ishan demurred involuntarily and moved away from the window. Dadar would be the next station and then Bombay Central. He arrived in Bombay after fifteen years, everything has completely changed. Ishan thought, "I still have to work out something in this alien world, this mess!" (Patel 8). He was surprised; he continued to look out of the train. He got off at Bombay Central Station and stood for a while. He picked up his bags! He walked out of the station. He gets the cab; he handed over the printed tariff

card. He carefully verified the name of the house, “Padmarag, fifth floor, Ashutosh Parikh” (Patel 9). He reached the home; he rang the doorbell and after a few moments the door was opened fully. Ashutosh neither welcomed nor inhospitable, he stared at Ishan, “Who was bereft of long hair, beard and moustache and said, “I hope the train was on time?” “Yes” (Patel 10). Sitaram got the luggage from him.

Rainbow at Noon depicts the selfishness of human beings. Ashutosh and Arnava are brothers of Ishan, when he entered Ashutosh’s house, he was upset. He had begun to dial his brother Arnava, his wife Reema stood before him with a look of suspicion and monitoring everything. He called:

Hello Arnava! He is here!”

“Really? How does he look? What? So, did he say anything like how long he intends to stay, what he plans to do?”

“No! I didn’t care to ask”

“That’s sensible in a way,”

“This is not entirely my responsibility; I hope you understand that?”

“Yes, but you are older” (Patel 11). Ashutosh looked at Reema, he knew that she did not like him but there was no alternative. Sitaram is a servant, he took care on Ishan. Mihika is a daughter of Reema and Kiran is a son. Mihika was extremely good-looking. She had barely crossed fifteen when the boys began to lower around her. She is studying first-year junior college. Mihika and Kiran were exchanging few things but they did not speak directly to Ishan. Modern boys were wasting their time; Kiran was playing a video game, and Mihika was busy with phone calls. Mihika and Kiran want to speak with their uncle Ishan but their parents were not allowing them. Reema was worrying her children, she thought that Ishan’s philosophy will influence on her children.

Rainbow at Noon depicts the nature of modern society. The modern man and woman are selfish; there is no good human relation and sentiments. Arnava visits his brother Ashutosh’s house, two brothers discuss Ishan. Ishan was busy, he was mediating. Ashutoshbhai asked him “Why don’t you say something?” But he did not reply. So he was so angry, he asked, “So, Ishan, what is your plan now?” (Patel 23). But he replied nothing. Ashubhai wants to send Ishan to Arnava’s house but he is very clear, he says to his brother,

“I have just three bedrooms. One is for us, one for Nancy and then there is the guest room.... but nobody can stay in it. If any guest lands up suddenly it becomes a problem Ashubhai, however, has one extra room” (Patel 24). Ishan left home and went away because his mother had passed away, now he returns from the ashram because his Guruji passed away. Arnava is very selfish, he wants escape from him. He told a lie about his wife and escaped. Children are very good; they are not selfish like men and women. Ashutosh’s children are kind-hearted and they liked their uncle. They shared the ideas with their friends proudly, “You know what; my uncle has become a *Sadhu*! He lives in the Himalayan Caves” (Patel 26). *Sadhu* purified the atmosphere with the chanting of some mantras and assumed the lotus position on the floor. The modern man is highly selfish and corrupt. There is no sentiment, human touch, kindness and helping nature.

There was a heated discussion between Arnava and Ashutosh about Ishan. Arnava had stopped laughing and he had inaugurated the main subject, “Since Bapuji’s demise, and all family affairs are being managed by you. Therefore, this is clearly your responsibility. Of course, I have come here to help you. But that’s about all. I don’t really figure!” “That’s great! If he is my brother, he is your brother too, isn’t he? Doesn’t that make you responsible?” “Alright then, now that you are talking like this, I ask you, did I get anything out of the ancestral inheritance? “Oh really? How can you say you got nothing? Who bare all the expenditure of sending you to America for your studies?” (Patel 27). Arnava is cunning and greedy, he tells lie, “Shala is very eager to see him” “You are welcome to take him” Reema offered” (Patel 28). He is not willing to take his brother but simply tells many reasons like her daughter Nancy’s examination is very close and he has to attend the job. Ishan continued reading and meditation. His brothers and their wives were worrying about Ishan, how to kick him from their house? Reema was so angry Ashutosh promptly declared. “Let’s think of all this at leisure after a week or so. Let him stay here for the time being” (Patel 31). She was angry, her eyes widened in an instant but Ashutosh was not paying attention. Ishan was innocent, simply, he listened their discussion and he softly calmly, “If you are the least bit uncomfortable, I will go and stay somewhere else” (Patel 31). Ishan was light-hearted and relieved after he left. He put the book aside still unfinished and took out the diary that is unfinished. He took out the diary that contained the names

and addresses of disciples and devotees. Ishan is now in Trishanku, he feels that, “Once you adopted *Sannayas*, you had no right left, over this house; there is no doubt about this. Similarly, after you renounced *Sannayas*, you no longer have any right to accept or donation from disciples and devotees which means something has to be done to earn a living” (Patel 33). Ishan is like a small baby; he needs parental support.

The society and brothers neglected a Sadhu, when his guru passed away; he had decided to leave the Ashrama. Soma Giri had inquired with greatest affection and concern, he replied, “For now, I am heading for Mumbai, “What next” “I don’t know!” (Patel 35). Ishan wants a job, but it is too difficult for him. When Ishan took a disksha, he tore all his certificates. He has passed B.A. but there is no proof to prove him. Man and Woman is greedy, selfish, and cunning in modern society. Shalmali is a wife of Arnava; she phoned to Reema and enquired about Ishan and bearing at home. Reema replies negatively, “Well that’s to you. If you want to come, you can come. If you want to take him with you, take him. Do what you wish. He is your husband’s brother too. Just as he is my husband! But if the two of you are planning on having lunch or dinner here, I don’t think. I will be able to manage that” (Patel 41). Ashubai and Arnava have discussed issues of Ishan, he had finished speaking. His heart was troubled with regret. Arnava suspects on his brother and he proved false and baseless. Ishan was very good person; he was simple and honest chap right from childhood. Ashutosh remembered his goodness; he could not understand plants and trees. He studied meditation and finally Vedic text with complete concentration. He was charted everything in his mind.

Nancy and Shalmali visit Reema’s house. Nancy is younger than Mihika and Karan. Nancy was more sensible than Minika and Karan. Nancy suspects, “Mummy I don’t think he is a *Sadhu*. He does not wear ochre robes, no long hair. The necklace of Rudraksha beads is also conspicuously absent” (Patel 46). Mihika glared at Nancy and said, “Shut up! Is this the way to talk to Sadhu's uncle” (Patel 47). Nancy was not apologetic, “Listen, I now think he is neither a *Sadhu* nor an uncle. Because he doesn’t look like my Daddy. Besides, if those people did not throw him out, what was the need for him to come here? Am I right, Mammy?” (Patel 48-49).

Rainbow at Noon depicts the good relationship between the teacher (guru) and his disciple. Ishan roused from his meditation and remembered the unbounded compassion of his Guru and his eyes brimmed with tears. Guruji had entrusted him with a task of translating a little Sanskrit book into Hindi and Gujarati. Guruji said, “It may be used of to someone sometime!” (Patel 52). Ishan started working on it, he took out the books and the papers and he arranged them neatly and carefully. He sat down and start work, Ashutosh asked him, “What are you doing Ishan? Have you begun to write something”?

‘No’ This is just a translation!”

“Who is going to publish it? How much will you make? Oh, I am sorry. I forgot you people don’t take money”.

“Well, that policy may not work anymore. But this one is the task entrusted by Guruji” (Patel 53). Ashutosh immediately sat down, he felt greatly relieved. Ashutosh speaks negatively and he discourages him. Ashutosh said, “Speak, brother!”

“I am aware my arriving like this, suddenly, without notice, may have got all of you thinking. Perhaps you are even worried. But there is no cause for concern really.”

“Well, that’s good!”

“Besides, I won’t stay in your house for long. In fact, today I identified a Mahadeva temple. The priest doesn’t mind putting me up in a small behind the temple. And he is letting me. Even though I am not in ochre robes” (Patel 54). Ishan speaks about the Ashrama; the Ashrama was in Uttar Kashi. He was bathed in the ice-cold Ganga even before dawn. He could not get peace without a bath; it was a remote place. He was facing the East and sitting in the lotus posture on the bank of the Ganga. He would chant the Gayatri mantra, and then he went to the ashram after that to hear the discourse from Gurudeva. They take roti and dal for lunch; they use more vegetables. Gurudeva eats vegetables with great joy. The Arati, bhajan, and meditation were scheduled at the evening time; every resident of the ashram was entitled to one wooden bowlful of milk at night. Swami Vivek Giri was the administrator of the Ashrama, he would purchase of more than a week’s provisions. Gurudeva said, “My dear fellow, *Kaliyuga* has struck, else, a day’s provisions would have been good enough for us” (Patel 57). Guruji received donations; that could be utilized for several noble purposes. The accommodation at the ashram could be

made extensive and appointed with amenities Ishan was very close to Guruji, he had fifteen years of constant company. Guruji imparts the supreme mantra of salvation to him alone before departing the mortal frame. Omkar Giri would entrust several new disciples with Ishan's care, he said, "Make him like you. Prepare him and bring him to me when he is ready. Guru will give the mantra.... and you listen up! Always abide by Ishan Baba's instructions, your welfare lies in it" (Patel 59). Ishan found the spiritual superintending identified to fetching Ganga water, it was as imperative as any of Guru's commands. One day after evening prayer Ishan was sitting next to Guru, and he said, "Listen, you have all renounced your homes and come here..... you must reach the destination! Whether your stay in this ashram or somewhere else, keep making progress. Do not tarry until you reach it. Is that clear? If ever there's any difficulty, just consult Ishan Baba. He will guide you properly" (Patel 59). There was a big silence.

Rain at Noon depicts the willpower and the future of *Sadhus* in India. Sannyasis are intelligent; they know their birth and death. Omkar Giri was a Sannyasi, he was a guru of Ishan. Ishan was loving disciple, one deep night Omkar Giri called Ishan and made him to sit very close to his own seat and said, "Exactly at three thirty, I shall depart. Listen, I don't want any weeping and wailing. Just sit next to me and chant the Omkar, the Primal sound. You will chant it for me, won't you?" (Patel 60). Ishan has politely agreed, it was Guru's command. He did not question, he followed it at the final hour. Ishan intoned Omkar with solemn one-pointedness; his primal sound resonated with blessing gravity. The process of Samadhi was completed and Gurudeva merged with the universe without a tear in his eyes he bid farewell to his Guru. There was a big discussion between the disciples of Pratap Giri and of Ishan. Who should ensure regarding occasion to the Master's seat, Ishan communicated his feelings to Vivek Giri and other Sadhus that, "I don't want anything; it does not matter if Pratap Giri becomes the head of the ashram" (Patel 60). Pratap Giri knows that Ishan's presence would be impossible for his enjoy of peace of mind. Ishan knows that, "Jealousy and envy did not become even a worldly person; there was no question of fanning these sentiments in a Sannyasi's life" (Patel 61). Ishan had decided to leave the ashrama, Vivek Giri, Soma Giri, and a few others were not happy.

Ishan was leading a simple life; he slept on the floor. He woke up early and did meditation. He felt that he was enjoying Gurudev's presence and his spiritual journey had no break. Ishan was very sensitive; he was involved in the translation work. He felt uneasy; something was pricking at his mind, "Coming here has been a mistake. I have increased my brother's murders. Now I must find accumulation somewhere as soon as possible" (Patel 64). He was searching a small place to live and provisions for moderate meals. He felt light hearted, he had turned very calm, sensitive and he sat down to do the translation work. Everything was written automatically, and several hours passed. He is highly disciplined he desirously sat down to his meal after chanting the verse in the Bhagwad Gita. His mother's demise, after demises his mother, he felt that "The bondage he had in this world had snapped" (Patel 69). He was free to do anything, there was no one left in the world. Who would either stop him or shed tears for his sake? Ishan could not find a single photo of his mother; he had a desire to see his mother's image. He remembered his Guru repeatedly said, that, "I am still like a child at your bosom, I commit myself to your case" (Patel 70). The present condition is different; Ashutosh's house was filled with clamorous and defensive Western music at a volume that shook the walls. He began to hear it with astonishment; he was worrying about modern society, "What was it? And why was the volume turned up so high?" (Patel 70). When Ishan was reading Sitaram served some milk and said, "Sethji has got the typewriter. .. do you want it how?" (Patel 71). But Ashan replied negatively.

Rainbow at Noon depicts the nature of modern society. The concept of trust has disappeared in the present society; there is no truth and trust in the present society. Ashubhai and Arnava have collected personal information of Ishan, they do not believe their own people but they believe others. Arnava has collected false information about Ishan, he telephoned his brother Ashubhai and narrated "Come on, first listen to this. Our brother is no *Sadhu*. Pandya straight away met the head. His name is Pratap Giri Maharaj. He didn't really give a decent report; you see I believe he said Ishan was sort of turned out of the *Ashram*" (Patel 72). Arnava suspected but Ashubhai would not believe it. Ashubhai would not believe, he said, "I feel we should take Ishan there and clarify things for to face. I don't think we need to invite any trouble after this. What do you think" (Patel 75)?

Rainbow at Noon depicts the cruel and suspicious nature of human beings. Reema has quarreled with her husband for the sake of Ishan; she has decided to take leave from the house. Ashutosh asked, “What’s the matter? What happened?”

“I am leaving” Reema declared curtly

“Come on! Where are you going? Why don’t you say something?”

“What’s the use of talking? You just don’t wish to do anything. Whatever the decision, I would have to accept it. So, I have decided I am taking the children and leaving for my brother’s place” (Patel 74). Reema was worrying about Ishan’s philosophy, she thinks that he may influence her children, Ashutosh wanted to say something but she started crying and blabbered as she cried, “I don’t want my son to become a *Sadhu* or *Bairagi*, I am taking him away. I will put him in a hostel; I’ll do whatever I can” (Patel 75). Ashutosh conveyed to Reema, he said, “I will send him off to Arnav’s today, okay? Are you happy? Come on, now sit here quality” (Patel 75). She was quite happy; she was staring at the open cupboard. Ashutosh held her hand and said, “You wind up all of this later, come and have some tea now” (Patel 76). Ishan was a great person and he loved his motherland. He loved even family members and he was busy with translating work. Karan courageously entered Sadhu’s room, he called affectionately. He listens to everything and he asks, “Is the headache severe? Come here, I’ll put an end to it” (Patel 77). Sadhu placed his hands on his head and pressed two veins beneath the ears on either side of the face. The headache vanished. Karan speaks negatively about his mother but Ishan says “Karan, never say such a thing again. You don’t know mothers. You have no idea how much they love their children...., they cannot stand any harm to them. They are ready to die for their children” (Patel 78). Ashutosh has decided to take Ishan to Arnav’s house; he gave some money to Sitaram before he departed.

Ishan moves to Shalmala and Arnav’s house, they live in a very prestigious flat. It has been named “The Nest”, the topmost floor belonged to just one person, who is considered to be one of the weal thieves’ people in Mumbai. Ishan was holding his luggage in his hand; he did not know where to keep it down. He looked like a country rustic in the spacious hall, Shalmali and her husband treated him very badly. She keeps Ishan with her servant Francis, Ishan is so happy living with Francis. Ashutosh so happily left Ishan; he

felt his entire world was lost to him. Somewhere in the depths of her heart, she felt that “What she was doing was not right” (Patel 89) He came at the time of cooking; she could have offered Ishan something. He was her brother-in-law. Francis was a cook; Ishan keeps a good relation with Francis. He had to render service to Nancy, who had returned from school and he had attended to the Kitchen duties too. Arnava, Shalmali, and Ishan go out and the three of them go down the multi-colored elevator with the thick carpet. Ipsita, a daughter of Mancklal, she recognized Ishan Baba. She exclaimed, “Ishan Baba, is that you?” (Patel 93). She bent low at his feet while Ishan stepped back. Niranjnanabhai’s daughter Ipsita recognised him. She met Niranjnanabhai holding both his hands tight and she observed resolutely, “There must be some reason for it, Papa! We lived in Uttar Kashi in the Himalayas in his company for so long that we learned so much from him. How can I forget his face? I am sure even Rajat will say that he is Ishan Baba” (Patel 95-96). Rajat was completely immovable, he could not speak and perhaps he could not hear either. He was a twenty-four-year-old youth with big inquisitive eyes. He could not recognize anyone.

Rainbow at Noon depicts honour of goodness and skill in Indian society. Niranjnan is a businessman, Niranjnan’s invitation, “Mr, Parikh, if you convenient to your guest, we would request you to bring him along at eight thirty for tea” (Patel 98). Arnava, Shalmala, and Ishan attended the invitation, Miss. Maneklal touched Ishan’s feet, Arnava felt proud of the fact that Ishan was his brother. Shalmal felt that the invitation had come because of him. *Rainbow at Noon* depicts the selfishness of man when Niranjnanabhai wants to meet Ishan. Arnava orders Francis, “Come on Francis, pick up his belongings and put them in the guest room” “But” “No arguments from now on, you shall stay there” (Patel 103). Francis’ face fell that, “Ishan was like personal property here; but when Ishan laughed and playfully told him, “Come brother, let’s pitch the tent there! He felt the burden lift from his heart” (Patel 103). Ishan read aloud from the copy of the Bible. Ishan shifted to Arnava’s beautiful unused guest room; there were two big windows, a double bed, table and chair, cupboard, dressing room, air conditioning fan and carpet. His luggage was arranged neatly. There was a gentleman of about fifty-five or thereabout with him; Ishan joined his hands and greeting. The elderly man returned and greeted, “I had a desire to meet you. From the time my daughter saw you yesterday, she has been remembering you constantly. I thought I

should call on you personally” (Patel 107). Niranjanbhai comes and requests Ishan to visit his place, and Ishan agrees. Ishan accompanied Niranjanbhai to her house, Ipsita quickly rushed to him and offered obeisance by bending low. Ishan visits Rajat’s room, it is spacious and it is like a hall. Ishan spoke in solemn tones, “Rajit” Ishan could not be sure whether Rajan’s eyes actually turned in his direction or they just seemed. Ishan concentrated all his vital energies and called “Rajat. The miracle had happened that Ranjit opened the eyes; his lips quivered with ease with them. Ishan was optimist; he smiled every time and said, “Sure, do!” (Patel 111). Ipsita was extremely happy; she had full faith in Guruji that Rajat would get well. They strongly believed that, “God had sent Ishan Baba here expressly for the purpose. It did not matter if he grew hair or wore white clothes, he was still Ishan Baba” (Patel 111).

Rainbow at Noon depicts the failure of modern medicine. Modern medicine does not cure any disease but the spiritual prayer and ‘Japa’ will cure all the diseases. Ishan asked Rajat’s father, “What’s he suffering from?” he replied, “There’s something wrong with the nervous system. Doctors suspected it and predicted several diseases but all we can say for sure is that he is deteriorating. We can’t even determine the extent to which he is conscious” (Patel 112). Niranjanbhai took Rajat to many hospitals, where doctors did many tests and gave many treatments but he was not cured. One of the senior doctors visits him once a day. The modern doctors were unable to find a disease, they helplessly said, “Let’s see what can be done. Treatment is on, but there is no guarantee” (Patel 112). Niranjanbhai has lost the hope, he requests Ishan “Baba. Please stay with us as long as Rajat is here” (Patel 113). Ishan assured him to stay at Niranjanbhai’s house. He requests Baba to get permission from Arnava and he replies, “Ishan knows that Arnavabhai would promptly agree. In fact, this meant freedom for him” (Patel 114). Ishan stays next to Rajat’s room. His illness brought the tenderness of the spirit and introspectiveness. Doctor Marshal was a senior doctor; he was of medium height and fair. He looked more like a banker or a professor than a doctor. He wished him and Ishan's request to Doctor, “I am happy you are here but promise me, you won’t stop the medicine” (Patel 117). The doctor was relieved; he has seen many cases cured by Ayurvedic medicine and spiritual Japan. Mohammedan healers, Sadhu babas, workers of charms and spells and astrologers together they had

ruined every advantage of science” (Patel 118). He firmly believed that as long as there was even one percent chance of recovering for the patient, the medicine should not be discontinued.

Rainbow at Noon depicts the significance of the ‘Prayer’ and the ‘Japa’. These are more powerful than the modern medicine. There was a big discussion between Doctor and Ishan, Ishan said frankly, “I am not a doctor and this is not my subject in any case. You are welcome to treat him the way you like. I will not come in the way.”

“What are you going to do there” Dr. Marshal asked

“Nothing at all. Just prayer and japa.”

“What happens as a consequence of these?”

“We will see, sometimes waves of strong resolve touch the consciousness of the patient; this could arouse the desire to live” (Patel 118). The discussion was taking place in English by Rajat’s bedside but he could not hear a thing. The doctor released, Ishan would not attempt to give food, drink, or medicine and the Doctor wished him. Ishan started prayer and Japa, which would cure Rajat. Rajat has moved his hand and clasped Ishan’s finger. The nurse could not believe her eyes; she gaped on incredulously, “I can’t believe it!” Ishan said lovingly, Rajat! My child, I sit next to you?” (Patel 120). Rajat opened and closed his eyes a couple of times, Ishan placed his hand on his head and said, “Now, you sleep Rajat! I am sitting right next to you. I am going anywhere. I’ll be here. Near you come. Relief mentally, I am not the bag of flesh and bones, “I am imperishable, indestructible Brahma that transcends all the three tensor. I am of the nature of supreme joy. I am all-powerful. I am not the body; I am the soul. I have no infancy and adolescence. I suffer no affliction. No death. No sorrow. No fear. I am the external consciousness that pervades the moveable and immovable world, chant with me. *Aum Hari, Aum...*” (Patel 121).

Rainbow at Noon depicts the significance of the Brahma Jnana. There was Rajat, Ispita, Niranjanbhai, Doctor Marshal, the nurse and a couple of additional servants, they were speaking in a low tone but now even a gaze was a burden to Ishan. Ishan sat on the corner of the bed, the pride of the door-ship had finally stung him, “What was the need for him to act as a go-between? Why did he have to forcefully rouse the consciousness that

was intent upon drawing? The *Brahma Jnana*, ultimate knowledge, with which he enticed Rajat to turn back did he have enough of that knowledge to lavish on another?" (Patel 123). Ishan felt that he laughed within. He wiped his tears and sat up; he felt pins and needles in his feet. There is no space for good people in India and people strongly believed in an evil-minded people. Francis kissed both Ishan's hands identically, he exclaimed, "God will never forgive their devilish people. But you don't worry Father. I'll take you to Goa. Nobody can touch you there. And I'll render service to you. I will do whatever you tell me to. I won't touch up the bottle, I promise Father!" (Patel 124). Ishan asked him, "What is the matter Francis" Francis hung his face down in shame; he had overheard the conversation between the two brothers in the presence of Pandya at Arnavas's house, "Pradeep Giri had falsely accused Ishan on theft" (Patel 124). Francis narrated a few things and finally declared, "I won't stay there anymore! The elder brother is tolerable, but my boss" (Patel 125). Ishan was not upset but he smiled. This is because new things usually come to pass in this world, this world was populated largely with people like Pratap Giri, and while they were speaking about worldly matters, they were forgetting time and space. He remembered his Guru's memory had turned into a delicate fragrance of Parijata flower and spread all around. Niranjanbhai requested Baba to protect his son, and Baba assured him. Rajat was cured Chhagan met Baba he shared his dream. He met a snake in dream and gets a remedy. When Rajat was cured, the news was spreading. Many people visit Baba and get medicine.

In Ishan's life journey, there was another turn. Soma Giri visits Ishan and explains the condition of the Ashrama. Many Sadhus were angry in the ashrama. There was anger at Pratap Giri's handling of the ashram's affairs. The static atmosphere of Guruji's time, characterized by peace and equanimity had been destroyed. In the place of severe asceticism to gain self-knowledge, there was now a strange current of transgressions, languorous, and worldly desire. There was no disciple in the ashram, Sadhu lives according to Pratap Giri's guidance. Many Sadhus are thinking of starting a new Ashrama, Soma Giri requests him, "Well then, you must return to the *Ashram Baba*" (Patel 159). Vivek Giri is also an advanced saint but he does not like the impropriety of Pratap Giri's actions but he does not say anything. Ishan was in dilemma, he told Soma Giri, "I don't know. Do rest

now. I have to complete this book. Please take it along when you go to the ashrama tomorrow and hand it over to Pratap Giri". "What will do? I don't know. Guruji had entrusted this task to me, He had said it would be of use to someone sometime. *Well, Hari Aum! Hari Aum!*" (Patel 161-162). Ishas was busy with some translation work, he did the work.

Rainbow of Noon depicts the Selfishness of modern society. When Rajat was cured, Ishan was very popular with Sadhu. Ishan's brothers visited and discussed some matters. Ashutosh met Ishan and requested, "Look here, Ishan! As soon as you leave this place, you will come and stay with us. Is that clear?" (Patel 165). *Rainbow at Noon* depicts the modern man's selfishness. When Ishan was so popular, Niranjambhai and Doctor decided to take him to Switzerland and earn a lot of money. His brother also runs a meditation class and earns a lot of money. Arnavas began to speak to Ishan, "I have been getting all the news. These people are out to smuggle you to Switzerland I am not going to allow this. They can't monopolize you. You are my brother!" (Patel 165). Ashutosh growled, "Ishan I have made all the arrangements for your mediation classes. I will manage the whole show" (Patel 165). Both brothers put a lot of fear in Ishan but he did not care for them. They talked of the police and the crime and other things but Ishan was silent. Ishan did a lot of work, he has translated much work and he said the significance of a book, "The Bhagwad Gita was enough; everything was learned by heart nevertheless one felt better with books around. Books feel like the company of intimate friends. One did not feel so lonely" (Patel 170). *Rainbow at Noon* concludes with Karan who wants to speak with Sadhu, he says, "Sadhu uncle, I have come specially to see you. Don't go to Nancy's house. She is no good. It would be better if you come to our place. You'll come, won't you?" (Patel 180). Ishan did not answer, he was in his own world and chanting, "We will throw a big party. I am going to call all my friends. They will like you very much. They like you Sadhu uncle?" (Patel 180). Karan requests Ishan to come to his home but Ishan rejects and Karan expresses his inner suffering and the nature of his parents. Karan met Ishan and shared Ice-cream and he said, "It is okay! You must go. You need not come to our place. You won't like it at our none of us like it. We are not happy, Sadhu Uncle!" Nobody is happy over these! The place you are going will you be happy there, Sadhu Uncle!" "I hope So." "I

hope you will be, but I will miss you, Sadhu uncle! And I'll come to see you once. Please send me your address" "Alright" (Patel 182). Ishan voiced his appreciation and walked towards the station. A wave rose in his mind.

Work Cited

Patil, Dhiruben. *Rainbow at Noon*. Trans. Ka. Raj Supe. Mumbai: Celestial Books, 2010.
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